

The Evolution of the Buffalo State Asylum

Paranormal phenomena have been around for centuries, yet are still widely misunderstood. Many rebuke it saying there's no scientific backing and on the contrary others are firm believers of it. Interpretations of paranormal phenomena rely solely on the perspective of the person, which is why it is so controversial. This phenomena is an experience many find unbelievable. To put it simply, a paranormal phenomenon is an unusual event or experience with no scientific explanation that is described by individuals as unnatural. It's an experience many find unbelievable and it is often linked to the supernatural such as ghosts. People often associate these phenomena with places like state hospitals due to the tragic histories there. An example of this is the Buffalo State Asylum in New York. Based on the research of this asylum, the events occurring at the asylum have purely sprouted from the fear and unease of these places rather than any solid evidence.

Most say, the Haunting of the Buffalo State Asylum started when the doors of the hospital first opened in December of 1880. Despite this, stories of paranormal phenomena that occurred in the Buffalo State Asylum have no specific date of occurrence as most reports of these phenomena came after the asylum was already abandoned. Originally built in the late 1880s, the hospital was located in the Richardson-Olmsted Campus in Buffalo, New York and designed by H.H Richardson and the grounds designed by Frederick Law Olmsted. The opening of the asylum as stated in *The American Journal of Insanity*, "Began fulfilling its mission by relieving another institution of its accumulation of patients of Western New York" (Andrews, 5). The asylum was built because the closest asylum was far away in Utica in central New York which would not be cost effective or easy for most patients to go there. However, the

infrastructure of the building couldn't hold more than 600 patients and it got too overcrowded with patients (Andrews, 6). This added to the incapability of treating every patient with equity. The harsh conditions, the setting, and the time period of the asylum helped create a perfect atmosphere for stories and rumors of paranormal phenomena and alleged hauntings. As a result of the haunting of the hospital many unreliable accounts of eyewitnesses arose.

Like many other asylums, the Buffalo State Hospital treated their patients with inhumane and ineffective treatments. In the 20th century, mentally ill people were treated unfairly as they were misunderstood and received inadequate treatment like the Buffalo State Hospital provided. Abusive treatments of the asylum and creepy feelings people have from the asylum are frequent reports received from eyewitnesses. An example of abuse is when John Turney, a patient there, was choked with towels unjustly and lost consciousness (Stuhler). Many people feel uneasy when around the psychiatric hospital due its tragic history and long abandonment. As stated in the *Skeptical Inquirer*, " 'When we saw a sign for the morgue I said, 'Screw this! I need to get out!' She said she was overwhelmed by fear. '...I wanted to die' " (Nickell, 2). Despite not seeing any ghosts, eyewitnesses like the young women still felt the abandoned hospital was eerie. She described it as, " 'Someone snapped their fingers and everyone disappeared' " (Nickell, 2). It is important to note that this young woman broke into the asylum with her friends expecting ghostly sightings. Most eyewitness reports are not trustworthy and came from fear of the hospital or an expectation of something paranormal like the example shown. Many others also feel that these claims of the asylum are untrue too.

In response to these claims of paranormal activity, people reacted with a mix of belief and skepticism. Some individuals liked the idea of a haunted asylum while others say that these claims are made up because people want to believe that an abandoned psychiatric hospital is

haunted. There are even some people who are offended by these claims and want historical accuracy to the name of the once Buffalo State Hospital. One of the staff at the Richardson Corporation stated, “We will not pursue ghost hunting, horror films, or paranormal endeavors...we want people to experience the authentic story, and respect what this was” (Rodriguez, 1). People like the staff of this nonprofit dedicated to preserving the landmark of the Buffalo asylum, and the locals of the town who know this hospital the best dismiss these untrustworthy claims. Misconceptions of the asylum are the main reason why these claims arose and many are aware of this which is why they don't believe in these claims. A neglected psychiatric hospital that once used misguided treatments like shock therapy or forced sterilization on mentally ill people evokes strong emotions in many. The claims of paranormal phenomena show the lack of respect people have towards the history of the asylum. People do not treat it as a landmark but rather as a place where they can break in and tell stories of ghosts. The media and government like the people are also split as they either try to preserve the history of the asylum by discouraging these claims or encourage these behaviors.

The media had a more outspoken response than the government regarding the asylum and these claims. The Buffalo State Hospital had no national level of responses from either but received state and town level responses. Once the patients of the asylum were moved and the asylum was abandoned there was no response from the national government or evidence of it. Though no former response, the town and city leaders tried to repurpose and preserve the history of the Buffalo State Hospital as a landmark. They did this by opening it to the public, repurposing a portion of the asylum into a hotel, and creating a non-profit organization called the Richardson Olmsted Campus to support the asylum. The town even created a detailed plan of the restoration of the asylum stating that the asylum will provide opportunities for public use and

economic development (Chan). Despite the claims of paranormal activity the government and city ignored the misconceptions many had towards the asylum. However, the media on the other hand focused on presenting the information of the asylum and its claims of paranormal activity as exciting as possible for the people. They reported stories of abuse, reports of paranormal, treatment of patients, and the history of the asylum in a way to give the public strong emotions by exaggerating the reports. Most of the time, people are just afraid of the asylum and the patients that used to be treated there so they imagine scary ghosts because of that. However, articles and newspapers manipulate the claims of what really happened and use this fear to sell out more. Due to the efforts of the government, sightings and incidents have decreased but at the same time the coverage of the media helped encourage the spread of stories and rumors.

There have not been further specific sightings of the asylum but rather rumors or stories of it. The creepy sightings and paranormal incidents have died down now that the town has allowed access to the public to explore the once abandoned hospital and some parts are being repurposed for businesses like the Richardson Hotel. Rather being neglected, the town and community of people there at Buffalo are trying to revive the hospital. There are no recent reports of sightings as people are just spooked by the place now. Hotel attendant Dennis Murphy also reports no paranormal phenomena and he has spent a considerable amount of time at the hotel that used to be part of the asylum (Nickell, 2). The hospital still has a history of rumored hauntings that evoke strong emotions of fear from people and none can deny the horrible treatment that the hospital once has done. For example it is still rumored that former patients at the asylum roam the hospital's grounds and its underground tunnels (Nickell, 1). Nonetheless, people began to acknowledge that hospitals for the mentally ill abused their patients and because

of these places are viewed as haunted. The once abandoned Buffalo State Hospital is now viewed as a landmark with a rich history and architecture.

The Haunted Buffalo Asylum is now viewed as a haunted site with a historical and architectural significance. People view the asylum in awe for its rebirth and a sense of nostalgia of its past purpose. Many admire the building's history in mental health and its revolutionizing architecture which attracted many tourists. The government even designated the hospital as a National Historic Landmark in 1986 due to its architecture and history. The architect of the building received much praise for his work because not only did he make the hospital look great but followed a treatment plan in which he created a therapeutic environment to help the patients recover. As stated in a magazine article, "The complex was conceived with positive intentions—to make people well. It now provides the opportunity for people new to Buffalo to discover its architectural richness and complex history" (Wright, 2). The intricate details of the hospital make people remember the past but also be impressed by the beauty of it. People admire the asylum for its significance and impact it had on the community of Buffalo. Parts of the asylum are being used for a college, a hotel, and an architecture center which all help the people living there. Some still are conflicted with the abusive past the asylum had and can not get over it. For instance, a woman reported of the cruel misery she endured at the asylum saying how she was not able to have writing materials or freedom for anything (Takoyoshi, 13). Stereotypes of the asylum and stories like these of past patients bother a few, especially those who had relatives there in the past but the asylum is still viewed as a respected figure.

Research of the Buffalo State Asylum proves that the paranormal events occurring there have sprouted from the fear and unease of the place rather than any strong evidence. Naturally, the narrative of the abandoned psychiatric hospital with a history of torture attracts many ghost

hunters, fans of the paranormal, locals, and exaggerated stories. The lack of trustworthy evidence proves the haunting of the Buffalo State Asylum is a hoax. The nature of the hospital intrigues many which is why it is exploited for claims of paranormal phenomena. Humans always look for the unexplained and paranormal phenomena tend to be the one where everyone looks to first because of its lack of scientific backing. Paranormal phenomena are intriguing to all as many seek the thrill of exploring a haunted site or paranormal incident as a form of entertainment. Even so, understanding that paranormal phenomena, especially those at state hospitals should not be taken as a thrill or shape the perception of history and mental illnesses is crucial to understand for our present day society.

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